

INVESTIGATING THE FINANCIAL DETERMINANTS OF CORPORATE CASH HOLDINGS: EVIDENCE FROM FIXED EFFECTS REGRESSION METHOD

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Abstract

The current research paper investigates the financial determinants of corporate cash holdings using a sample of 83 listed manufacturing and services corporations in the Amman stock exchange – Jordan over the period, 2009 – 2020. The fixed effects regression method based on the results of the Hausman test is used for estimation purposes. However, the results indicated that there is a statistically significant negative effect of foreign ownership, investment policy, financial leverage, and networking capital on corporate cash holdings. Besides, the return on equity and the firm size has a statistically significant positive effect on the corporate cash holdings. This study has vital implications for the business managers to better understand the importance of corporate cash holdings and their determinants, especially in formulating financial policies in corporations.

Keywords: Corporate Cash Holdings; Fixed Effects Regression Method; Jordan.

GEL classifications: B26; C23; F38

1. Introduction

Foreign ownership has become an important source of capital due to the benefits of the presence of foreign investors in the domestic market, which enhances the local market liquidity. However, important decisions are taken by foreign investors to determine their ownership proportions (i.e., full ownership or shared ownership). Indeed, the choice of ownership is complicated because it is influenced by different variables. The relationship between foreign ownership and corporate cash holdings has been widely investigated (Al-Hadi et al., 2020; Al-Najjar, 2013; Chang & Tang, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Guizani, 2017; Gupta & Bedi, 2020; Hou & Liu, 2020). Cash holding is considered an important component of the current assets. It is the amount of cash held by companies to run their numerous activities for speculation, precaution, and transaction.

By the end of 2020, the ownership of foreign corporations listed in the Amman stock exchange (ASE) – Jordan formed about half of the total market capitalization (ASE annual report, 2021). Figure 1 displays the non-Jordanian ownership of market capitalization in ASE. In 2020, the shares owned by non-Jordanians represent 51.1% of ASE capitalization, where the Arab investors owned 32.5%, and the non-Arabs investors owned 18.6%. This implies that any failure in ASE and the Jordanian economy may have serious repercussions. Nevertheless, the current study attempts to examine the determinants of cash holdings for the Jordanian corporations listed on the ASE using the fixed effects regression method. These

determinants are foreign ownership, investment, networking capital, return on equity, firm size, and financial leverage. The importance of this research paper stems from the implications that are provided for policymakers, investors, financial management consultants, and academics. The remainder of this paper is presented as the following four sections. The second section presents review of literature. The third section outlines the research methodology. The fourth section discusses the analysis of results. The fifth section concludes the paper.

Figure 1. Non-Jordanian ownership of market capitalization (%) in ASE

Source: ASE

2. Literature review

Many researchers have made efforts to investigate the determinants of financial corporate cash holdings. This section attempts to shed the light on the major determinants of financial corporate cash holdings from the previous literature. Afza and Adnan (2007) examined the determinants of corporate cash holdings for non-financial Pakistani firms over the period, 1998 – 2005. The results showed that cash holdings were significantly affected by the firm size, net working capital, and financial leverage. Al-Hadi et al. (2020) examined the determinants of corporate cash holdings for a large sample of Gulf Cooperation Council corporations for 2005 – 2013. The results showed that the characteristics of the investment committee (i.e., committee size, number of meetings, independence, and member experience) increase the corporate cash holdings. Ahmed et al. (2018) examined the determinants of corporate cash holdings for a sample of 115 Chinese listed corporations over the period, 2012 – 2016. The results showed that financial leverage, managerial ownership, non-cash liquid assets, and bank debt negatively influenced corporate cash holdings. Besides, dividends and investment positively affected corporate cash holdings. Al-Najjar (2013) examined the

determinants of corporate cash holdings in developing countries, Brazil, Russia, India, and China, and compares the results with a sample of corporations from the USA and the UK. The results showed that capital structure, dividend policy, and firm size are important determinants of corporate cash holdings.

Chang and Tang (2020) studied the impact of corporate cash holdings on the total factor productivity using data for corporations in 65 countries over the period, 1993 – 2017. The results showed that total factor productivity was enhanced by higher corporate cash holdings. Chen et al. (2020) studied the impact of corporate governance on cash holdings in 41 countries. The results showed that board reforms were significantly decreased the cash holdings. Drobetz and Gruninger (2007) investigated the determinants of corporate cash holdings for Swiss non-financial corporations. The findings revealed that cash holdings were negatively related to firm size. Ferreira and Vilela (2004) examined the determinants of corporate cash holdings in the countries of economic and monetary union. The results showed that cash holdings were positively affected by investment opportunities.

Guizani (2017) investigated the determinants of corporate cash holdings for a sample of Saudi corporations over the period, 2006 – 2014. The results showed that cash flow volatility, net working capital, capital expenditures, firm size, and leverage are important determinants of corporate cash holdings. Gill and Shah (2012) investigated the determinants of corporate cash holdings using a sample of 166 Canadian listed corporations on the Toronto Stock exchange. The results showed that board size, firm size, financial leverage, net working capital, and market to book ratio significantly influenced the corporate cash holdings. Gupta and Bedi (2020) investigated the relationships between promoter ownership and corporate cash holdings for a sample of non-financial corporations in India. The results showed that promoter ownership was negatively associated with cash holdings.

Hou and Liu (2020) examined the relationship between foreign residency rights and corporate cash holdings. The results showed that privately-owned enterprises whose controlling persons have foreign residency rights are holding more cash. Loncan (2020) investigated the effects of foreign institutional ownership on corporate cash holdings in emerging economies. The results showed that foreign ownership had a negative effect on cash holdings. Maheshwari and Rao (2017) examined the determinants of corporate cash holdings using a sample of 395 manufacturing and services corporations over the period, 2007-2012. The results indicated that dividend payment and market to book ratio positively influenced corporate cash holdings. Also, networking capital, investment, and financial leverage negatively influenced cash holdings. Saddour (2006) investigated the determinants of cash holdings for 297 French corporations over the period, 1998 – 2002. The results showed that cash holdings were negatively associated with firm size and financial leverage. Tayem (2017) investigated the determinants of corporate cash holdings in Jordan using a sample of listed non-financial corporations for the period, 2005 – 2013. The results showed that financial leverage was negatively associated with cash holdings

3. Research methodology

3.1. Data and variables

Table 1 shows the dataset of dependent and independent variables. The selection of variables is based on the empirical literature and the theories of corporate governance and working capital requirements i.e., free cash flow theory for Jensen (1986), pecking order theory for Myers and Majluf (1984), and tradeoff theory for Myers (1977). The sample of this study includes manufacturing and services corporations listed on ASE over the period, 2009 – 2020. In detail, 83 corporations are included in the analysis (42 services corporations and 41 manufacturing corporations). The financial sector has been excluded because some corporations are bankrupted and liquidated during the period 2009 – 2020.

Variable	Definition	Sort	of	Data collection
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Table 1: Variables of the study

		variable	
Corporate cash holdings (CCH)	The ratio of cash and cash equivalent to the total assets, which equals cash divided by net assets.	Dependent	https://www.ase.com.jo/en
Foreign ownership (FO)	The percentage of foreign ownership in the corporation.	Independent	
Investment (I)	Includes the firm's capital expenditures as well as acquisition expenditures, which equal net capital expenditures divided by total assets.		
Net Working capital (NWC)	Is the difference between current assets and current liabilities divided by total assets		
Return on equity (ROE)	The ratio that intends to measure the level of management effectiveness in generating profit, which equals net income divided by stockholders' equity.		
Firm size (FS)	Is calculated as the natural logarithm of total assets.		
Financial leverage (FL)	Defined as the total liabilities scaled by total assets.		

Source: Brigham and Ehrhardt (2005).

3.2. Research Model

The current paper investigates the determinants of corporate cash holding for the Jordanian listed corporations in ASE over the period, 2009 – 2020. Based on the F-statistics test and Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test (1980), the pooled ordinary least square regression method is inadequate. Thus, the panel data regression model is applied. Besides, the Hausman (1978) test has been used to decide whether to employ a random or fixed-effect model for the panel data regression. However, the determinants of the corporate cash holdings model are shown as in equation (1):

$$CCH_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FO_{i,t} + \beta_2 I_{i,t} + \beta_3 NWC_{i,t} + \beta_4 ROE_{i,t} + \beta_5 FS_{i,t} + \beta_6 FL_{i,t} + \beta_{7-12} \text{Year} + \text{Industry Dummies} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

where CCH is the dependent variable corporate cash holdings, α denotes the intercept term, β_{1-6} represent the coefficients of independent variables, FO is the foreign ownership, I denote the investment, NWC represents the net working capital, ROE denotes the return on equity, FS represents the firm size, FL denotes the financial leverage, β_{7-12} Year represent dummy variables, ε denotes the error term, i represents the corporation, t denotes the time (year).

4. Data analysis and discussions

The Pearson correlation matrix of the study's estimated model is shown in Table 2. The correlation between the pair of independent variables does not exceed 0.80. Thus, there is no evidence of multicollinearity between independent variables. Based on the results of the Hausman test (Chibar2 = 24.21, Probability > Chibar2 = 0.021), the null hypothesis is rejected because the probability is lower than 5%. Thus, the fixed-effect model is more appropriate than the random model to investigate the model of the study.

Table 2. Results of the Pearson correlation matrix

Variable → ↓	CCH	FO	I	NWC	ROE	FS	FL
CCH	1.00						
FO	0.40*	1.00					
I	-0.39*	0.10	1.00				
NWC	0.32**	0.13	0.42*	1.00			
ROE	0.29**	0.40*	0.22**	0.11	1.00		
FS	0.41*	0.36*	0.26**	0.09	0.06	1.00	
FL	-0.23*	0.33**	0.34*	0.06	0.05	0.38*	1.00

Source: E-views software package.

Note: *, ** means the significance at 1% and 5% levels (2-tailed), respectively.

Table 3. Results of fixed effects regression

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics	Probability
FO	-0.07	-3.23	0.001*
I	-0.11	-4.32	0.000*
NWC	-0.36	-3.98	0.001*
ROE	0.091	2.981	0.020**
FS	0.191	2.511	0.010*
FL	-0.27	-2.87	0.001*
Intercept	0.221	7.661	0.000*
R-squared	0.852	Durbin Watson statistics	1.511
Adjusted R-squared	0.842	Akaike information criterion	-2.23
F-statistics	36.30	Schwartz information	-1.61

		critierion	
Prob (F-statistics)	0.000*	Hannan–Quinn criterion	-1.52

Source: E-views software package.

Note: *, ** denotes the significance at 1% and 5% levels, respectively.

The results of the fixed effects regression are presented in Table 3. The results of Adjusted R-squared 84.2% showed that about 84% of the variation in the dependent variable (corporate cash holdings) is explained by independent variables (foreign ownership, investment, networking capital, return on equity, firm size, and financial leverage). Also, it is observed that the estimated model in equation (1) is statistically significant at 1% level with an F-statistics value of 36.30 (Prob = 0.000). The results in Table 3 indicated that there is a statistically significant negative effect of foreign ownership, investment policy, financial leverage, and networking capital on corporate cash holdings. Also, the return on equity and the firm size has a statistically significant positive effect on the corporate cash holdings.

The negative relationship between corporate cash holdings and foreign ownership indicates that when the level of cash holdings decreased, more economic resources are available and allocated to the growth of corporations. This result is consistent with the results obtained by (Benkraiem et al., 2020; Loncan, 2020). The significant negative relationship between corporate cash holdings and investment policy shows that when investment increases, corporate cash holdings will be decreased because it is employed to finance investments. This result is in line with the result obtained by (Dennis & McKeon, 2018). Both financial leverage and networking capital have a significant negative effect on corporate cash holdings. These results are consistent with (Afza & Adnan, 2007; Saddour, 2006). On the other hand, returns on equity and firm size are positively related to corporate cash holdings. These results are in line with (Lins et al., 2010).

5. Concluding remarks

This paper examined the determinants of corporate cash holdings using a sample of manufacturing and services corporations listed in Amman Stock Exchange over the period, 2009 – 2020. It employed the fixed effects regression analysis. The results showed that there is a statistically significant negative effect of foreign ownership, investment policy, financial leverage, and networking capital on corporate cash holdings. Also, the return on equity and the firm size has a statistically significant positive effect on the corporate cash holdings. The implications of this study would be valuable for investors, analysts, and business managers. The policymakers in Jordan should take into considerations the benefits of foreign investors for domestic corporations. The study also recommends the regulators on the ASE to pay more attention to the small corporations, because the corporate cash holdings is positively associated with the large size corporations. However, future research is supposed to use different sample and other variables to get a new perspective.

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